

заимствование звукового облика иноязычного выражения (каламбур): *мыло – электронная почта, аська – ICQ, клавиша – клавиатура.*

Вышли из профессиональной среды и стали общеупотребительными, например, такие слова: *бан (ограничение прав интернет-пользователя как способ наказания), биткоин (виртуальная валюта, криптовалюта), бот (специальная программа, которая автоматически выполняет те же действия, что и обычные интернет-пользователи), спойлер (преждевременно раскрыта важная информация, портящая впечатление, разрушает интригу), хайп (активное обсуждение, шумиха вокруг какой-то актуальной проблемы, события ради популярности).*

Многие слова приобрели новые устойчивые значения: *гость-незарегистрированный участник форума; комната-специальная страница, тематический раздел в чате; лазить (гулять, бродить, сидеть...).* Одни авторы считают, что сленг портит, загрязняет литературный язык, что это паразитный слой лексики, с которым необходимо бороться. Другие, наоборот, усматривают в нем элемент, который придает языку живости и образности, способствует его обогащению и совершенствованию.

6. Демократизация. Почти во всех сообщениях принято писать «вы» с маленькой буквы. «Вы» с прописной буквы выглядит анахронизмом. Не закрепились единые нормы использования обращения «коллеги» в переписке. Предлагают заменять обращением по имени и отчеству.

Лексические, морфологические и синтаксические особенности делового языка определяются основными чертами делового дискурса и варьируются в зависимости от жанра и содержания делового документа или высказывания.

Вывод. Русский язык - один из самых распространенных языков в профессиональной среде интернета. Для эффективной профессиональной коммуникации нужно контролировать деструктивные элементы и экспансию иноязычных слов.

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CONVERSION AND SHORTENING AS PRODUCTIVE TYPES OF WORD FORMATION IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: This study examines two productive types of word formation in English: conversion and shortening. Conversion, or zero derivation, involves changing a word's part of speech without altering its form, while shortening encompasses processes like clipping, acronyms, and blends that reduce the length of words. By analyzing these processes, this research highlights their roles in the dynamic evolution of the English lexicon. The study investigates examples from contemporary English, assesses their frequency and usage, and discusses implications for language teaching and learning.

Keywords: Conversion, zero derivation, shortening, clipping, acronyms, blends, word formation, English lexicon, language evolution.

Introduction. Word formation processes are crucial for the development and expansion of any language. Among the various mechanisms, conversion and shortening stand out due to their productivity and prevalence in English. Conversion allows for a word to change its grammatical category without any morphological change, while shortening reduces the length of words through clipping, acronyms, and blends. This article explores these processes, providing examples and discussing their implications for English language users.

Conversion. Mechanisms of Conversion:

Conversion, also known as zero derivation, involves shifting a word from one grammatical category to another without adding prefixes or suffixes. Common types include noun-to-verb, verb-to-noun, and adjective-to-verb conversions.

1. Noun-to-Verb Conversion

- Example: "Email" (noun) → "to email" (verb)
- Usage: "She will email the document."

2. Verb-to-Noun Conversion

- Example: "Run" (verb) → "a run" (noun)
- Usage: "He went for a run."

3. Adjective-to-Verb Conversion

- Example: "Clean" (adjective) → "to clean" (verb)
- Usage: "We need to clean the house."

Examples and Frequency. Conversion is widely used in contemporary English. High-frequency examples include:

- "Text" (noun) → "to text" (verb)
- "Google" (proper noun) → "to google" (verb)

Shortening. Mechanisms of Shortening:

Shortening involves reducing the length of words, making them more concise. The main types of shortening include clipping, acronyms, and blends.

1. Clipping

- Example: "Advertisement" → "ad"
- Usage: "I saw an ad for a new phone."

2. Acronyms

- Example: "NASA" (National Aeronautics and Space Administration)
- Usage: "NASA launched a new satellite."

3. Blends

- Example: "Brunch" (breakfast + lunch)
- Usage: "We had brunch at the new cafe."

Examples and Frequency. Shortening is particularly prevalent in informal and digital communication:

- "Gym" from "gymnasium"
- "Info" from "information"
- "Blog" from "weblog"

The productivity of conversion and shortening in English reflects the language's adaptability and efficiency. These processes enable the creation of new words and the evolution of the lexicon, making communication more effective and dynamic.

Implications for Language Teaching: Understanding conversion and shortening is vital for language learners as it aids in vocabulary expansion and comprehension. Teaching strategies should include:

1. Explicit Instruction: Clarify the mechanisms and provide numerous examples.
2. Practice Exercises: Engage students in identifying and using converted and shortened words.
3. Contextual Learning: Use real-life texts and digital communication examples to illustrate these processes.

Conclusion. Conversion and shortening are essential and highly productive word formation processes in the English language. Conversion, or zero derivation, allows words to change their grammatical category without morphological alteration, thus enhancing the language's flexibility and richness. Shortening, through mechanisms such as clipping, acronyms, and blends, simplifies communication by creating concise and efficient terms.

Both processes reflect the dynamic and adaptive nature of English, facilitating the continuous expansion and evolution of its lexicon. These word formation strategies not only enrich the language but also respond to the communicative needs of its users, especially in fast-paced and informal contexts such as digital communication and everyday speech.

For language learners, understanding these processes is crucial for developing a comprehensive vocabulary and achieving fluency. Effective language teaching should

therefore include explicit instruction on conversion and shortening, practical exercises for application, and the use of contextual examples to illustrate real-world usage.

By recognizing the importance and utility of conversion and shortening, educators can better equip students to navigate and master the evolving landscape of the English language, ultimately fostering greater linguistic competence and confidence.

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ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРОЛОГИЯ КАК СОВРЕМЕННОЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЕ ЛИНГВИСТИКИ И КУЛЬТУРОЛОГИИ

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